

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF CONTINUOUS NICKEL ALUMINATE - ALUMINUM PHASE COMPOSITE

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1. Introduction

Nickel aluminate (NiAl_2O_4) has an excellent strength and a good wet ability with metals at high temperature, besides the general merits spinel materials have [1,2]. In particular, the nickel aluminate having a porous structure can be used as a good ceramic skeleton for many applications. As one of them, a nickel aluminate ceramic – metal composite can be fabricated by infiltration of metals into the skeleton. The wet ability between ceramic and metal has been studied over the last decades [3,4], and a Lanxide process [5] was known as a representative method for making ceramic-metal composite. However, the study of the powder synthesis for the nickel aluminate has not been examined widely, but only in the limited field of solid state reaction or sol-gel synthesis [6,7]. Also the fabrication process for the composite consisted of a porous, sintered nickel aluminate and aluminum metal was not studied at all.

In this study, the nickel aluminate powder was synthesized by a new powder synthesis method, polymer solution technique [8,9]. And the porous nickel aluminate skeleton was fabricated by polyurethane foam process [10]. Sequentially, molten aluminum alloy was infiltrated into the porous nickel aluminate. The mechanical properties of the composites, which have a unique microstructure consisted of continuous phases of ceramic and metal, are examined according to the pore size of the nickel aluminate skeleton. A numerical study for the prediction of mechanical failure behavior of the composite is also performed under the modification of finite element code in DIANA [11].

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1 Preparation of Composite

Nickel nitrate and aluminum nitrate were dissolved in stoichiometric proportion in de-ionized (D.I.) water. Once the nitrates were completely dissolved, 5 wt% PVA solution was added. The D.I. water in the precursor sol was evaporated by continuous stirring during heating at 150 °C on a hot plate. The resulting gel-type precursors were completely dried, and calcined and crystallized at 900 °C in an air atmosphere in a box furnace. The as-synthesized powders were ball-milled with zirconia ball media for 6 h under a wet condition using isopropyl alcohol as a solvent.

To make nickel aluminate porous body, nickel aluminate slurry was fabricated by using the synthesized nickel aluminate powder containing 1 wt% PVA polymer. And then, polyurethane foams, which had different pore sizes, were dipped in the nickel aluminate slurry and were squeezed to remove the slurry from the sponge pores. The wet polyurethane foams were dried and calcined in air atmosphere at a slow heating rate for burn-out of the polyurethane skeleton. Finally, the calcined, porous nickel aluminate bodies were sintered at 1600 °C for 1 h in an air atmosphere.

Bulk aluminum alloys were melted on the porous nickel aluminate body in vacuum or nitrogen atmosphere at 1000 °C for the metal infiltration process. In this study, three kinds of alloys (a1~a3) were used and the composition of each alloy is listed in Table 1. The microstructures of the porous nickel aluminate and the composite interfaces were

Table 1. Composition of Aluminum Alloys (wt%).

	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Ti	V	Al
a1	0.149	0.575	0.191	0.003	0.001	0.013	0.013	99.04
a2	3.778	0.828	0.104	0.007	0.001	0.019	0.015	95.23
a3	0.206	0.593	0.165	1.211	4.200	0.017	0.012	93.58

examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi, S-3500N). The specimens were mounted on an aluminum stub and Au-Pd sputtered on 15 mA for 40 sec.

2.2 Mechanical Test

The flexural strengths of the nickel aluminate – aluminum composites were examined using a universal testing machine (model 4502, Instron Corp., Canton, MA). The bend-bars with dimensions of 30 mm × 2.5 mm × 3.0 mm were polished to a 15 μm finish with diamond paste. 4-point flexural testing was performed using a 9.0±0.1 mm inner span and a 20.0±0.1 mm outer span, at a crosshead speed of 0.01 mm/min. The nickel aluminate porous samples were also examined their compressive strengths with cubic-type samples.

2.3 Numerical Analysis

A numerical study was performed to estimate proper failure behavior of the composite on the basis of continuum materials, and to compare the results of mechanical test. Material properties required in the analysis were obtained from additional experimental data and reference data. Young's moduli of nickel aluminate and aluminum were taken as 198 GPa and 70 GPa, and also Poisson's ratios were 0.2 and 0.3, respectively. The estimated ceramic volume fraction was taken as 40 vol%. Numerical simulation was done by using a commercial finite element code DIANA [11], in which proper modifications were added to reflect the effects of filling rate of pores and combined bond strength of different materials in the sense of micro-mechanics.

3. Results and Discussion

Fine nickel aluminate powders were synthesized by the PVA solution route. The ball milling process with the nickel aluminate powders was quite effective in grinding the particles to sub-micron sizes. The precursor gels were aerated and the calcined powders were also soft and porous. The porous NiAl₂O₄ powders could be obtained by a polymer addition to the normal chemical solution method. Finally, the ball-milled nickel aluminate powder showed an average particle size of 0.28 μm with a specific surface area of 23.0 m²/g.

Porous nickel aluminate bodies were successfully fabricated by the polyurethane foam method. Several polyurethane foams, which have a different PPI (pore per inch), were used as the dipping media. A representative microstructure of the porous nickel aluminate is presented in Fig. 1. The open pores were distributed evenly with a channel-type connection and the skeleton thickness was uniform over the whole microstructure.

Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of porous nickel aluminate skeleton.

Fig. 2 shows the compressive strength of the porous nickel aluminate skeleton at different pore size. The compressive strength of the porous nickel aluminate was changed as a function of pore size. As expected on normal porous ceramics, the highest compressive

Fig. 2. Variation of compressive strength of porous nickel aluminate skeleton according to pore size.

strength of 8.1 MPa was obtained with the smallest pore size of 300 μm .

In the aluminum alloy infiltration process, all kinds of alloys (a1~a3) were infiltrated in vacuum atmosphere. However, the infiltration was not occurred uniformly through the whole samples. In particular, the wetting between nickel aluminate and aluminum was not enough to make dense interface. The representative microstructure of the poor interface bonding in vacuum atmosphere is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Interface microstructure of nickel aluminate - aluminum alloy composite heated in vacuum.

In the case of nitrogen atmosphere, the aluminum alloys of a1 and a2 were not infiltrated into the nickel aluminate skeleton, while the a3 was

infiltrated extensively through the whole skeleton sample. According to previous study [12], it has been known that oxidizing surface of molten aluminum prevents wetting reaction with ceramics. However, Mg in the molten aluminum inhibits the formation of the oxidation film. Particularly, it has been shown that the Mg reacted with nitrogen gas forms Mg-N compounds and they improve the wetting between molten aluminum and alumina ceramics. In this experiment, the nickel aluminate spinel was used instead of alumina, and the aluminum alloy (a3) containing enough amount of 4.2 wt% Mg was employed. Fig. 4 shows the interface microstructure of the nickel aluminate - aluminum (a3) composite heated in nitrogen atmosphere. The composite had a dense interface microstructure without pores. In the a3 aluminum alloy, the Mn and Mg worked as a wetting agent for good infiltration and wetting with the spinel ceramics [5].

The measured flexural strengths of the composite, prepared with the a3 aluminum alloy in nitrogen atmosphere, were ranged between 620 MPa to 490 MPa according to the pore size of nickel aluminate skeleton as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Interface microstructure of nickel aluminate - aluminum alloy composite heated in nitrogen atmosphere.

Fig. 5. Variation of flexural strength of nickel aluminate - aluminum composite according to pore size of ceramic skeleton.

The measured strength was enough higher than the strength of porous nickel aluminate skeleton. In the composites consisted of continuous phases of ceramic and metal, the strength was certainly affected the volume ratio of ceramic skeleton which is dependent on the pore size. As shown in Fig. 5, the strength was almost linearly decreased as the ceramic volume decreased.

The mechanical behavior of the composite having the complicate microstructure was examined by computational simulation. The result of numerical failure analysis showed a non-brittle fracture behavior as shown in Fig. 6. It was estimated in the assumption of 40 vol% nickel aluminate. The calculated strength was 525 MPa, and the data was close to the experimental, measured strength of the sample prepared with the skeleton having 600 µm pore size (Fig. 5).

Fig. 6. Displacement and load curve for numerical simulation in nickel aluminate ceramic – aluminum metal composite.

4. Conclusion

The continuous ceramic-metal phase composites were successfully fabricated. The aluminum alloy containing Mg and Mn was infiltrated into the nickel aluminate skeleton in nitrogen atmosphere at 1000 °C. The flexural strength of the composite was dependant on the pore size of the nickel aluminate skeleton, and a flexural strength of 620 MPa was obtained in the composite having a pore size of 300 µm, showing a non-brittle fracture behavior.

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